

Report 'Workshop Data Stewards Job Profiles: Build and Sustain Capacity for FAIR Implementation'

4 April 2023, Holland Heart House, Utrecht

Maastricht University

Maastricht UMC+

Radboudumc

Purpose of the meeting	2
Programme	2
Organising committee	3
Participants	3
Presentations / joint slide deck	3
Welcome & Opening	3
Maria Cruz / Hans de Jonge, Open Science NL	3
Sarah Coombs, Open Science advisor for the Universities of Applied Sciences	4
Introducing the NPOS-F report	4
Use Cases on data stewards job profile implementation	5
Radboudumc	5
Saxion University of Applied Sciences	7
Technical University Delft	8
Introduction to the international landscape	9
<i>EOSC & Data Stewardship</i> , by Celia van Gelder, co-chair of the 'Data stewardship, curricula and career paths Task Force'	9
<i>RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group</i> , by Yan Wang, IG co-chair	10
Conclusions	10
Next steps per recommendation for all organisations	11
Break out discussions	12

Purpose of the meeting

Two years after the first extensive report on the data steward profession was published, 30 representatives from a large number of Dutch research organisations got together at the Holland Heart House at Utrecht to discuss lessons learnt from the adoption and implementation of official data stewards job profiles in the Netherlands. The audience consisted of policy and decision makers, data steward coordinators and data stewards involved in building capacity for data stewardship within their organisations.

The “Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education – Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship” [report](#) was written in the context of the Dutch National Plan Open Science. Acknowledging that data stewardship is essential to fulfill national and European ambitions on Open Science and FAIR, the NPOS project F team thoroughly explored the existing data stewardship landscape, described the variety of competencies and skills that data stewards need and flagged gaps in the education and training needed for the role. Also, it drafted a first official data steward job profile, which had a great impact on the professionalisation and acknowledgement of data stewardship, not only in the Netherlands but world-wide. In the workshop, progress was discussed regarding the reports’ recommendations as well as the recommendations from the [‘Handreiking voor de Organisatie van Datastewardship voor praktijkgericht onderzoek van hogescholen’](#) (2022).

Programme

13.00 – 13.20 Welcome and opening by Hans de Jonge, Quartermaster-Director Regieorgaan Open Science & Sarah Coombs, Open Science advisor for the Universities of Applied Sciences.

13.20 – 13.30 Introduction to the 2021 “Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education” report, its recommendations, and the Data stewards job profile; Mijke Jetten, Health-RI

13.30 – 14.15 Use cases on data stewards job profile implementation

- Radboudumc, Peter-Bram ‘t Hoen
- Saxion UoAS, Renate Mattizik
- TU Delft, Yan Wang

14.15 – 14.30 Introduction to the international landscape

- EOSC Task Force on Data Stewardship; Celia van Gelder, TDCC LSH / Health-RI
- RDA Professionalising Data Stewards Interest Group; Yan Wang, TU Delft

14.30 – 14.50 Coffee / tea break

14.50- 15.40 Break out discussions, topics:

1. How to successfully implement the data stewards job profile and recruit data stewards?

2. How to organise national training and collaborate to increase capacity?

15.40 – 16.00 Central wrap-up and future actions

Organising committee

- Celia van Gelder, TDCC LSH / Health-RI
- Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Radboudumc
- Renate Mattisziik, Saxion / DCC PO
- Annemie Mordant, Maastricht University / MUMC+
- Fieke Schoots, TDCC LSH / Health-RI
- Yan Wang, TU Delft

Participants

- Anne-Lotte Masson, ErasmusMC
- Maria Cruz, NWO
- Marcel Ras / VU Amsterdam
- Andrew S. Hoffman, Data Steward, Faculty of Social Sciences, Leiden University
- Marjan Grootveld, DANS
- Mijke Jetten, Health-RI
- et al.

[Joint slide deck](#)

Welcome & Opening

Maria Cruz / Hans de Jonge, Open Science NL

Maria Cruz, Programme Leader Open Research Software opened the meeting, replacing Hans de Jonge, director of Open Science NL. Open Science NL was officially launched on the 23rd of March to further accelerate the transition to open science in the Netherlands with the goal of making Open Science the norm. This will be done:

- By providing (temporary) funding for projects, initiatives, and infrastructures
- By monitoring and evaluating progress
- By providing a forum for exchange of best practice
- By organising and facilitating coordination on national level

The NPOS 2030 ambitions and rolling agenda document provides an overall framework for the Work Programme 2023- 2024 to be approved by the Steering board after consultation with the community. Funding instruments will be developed, tailored to the needs of the topics and the community. Hans and Maria expressed some personal concerns as to the sustainability of data stewardship capacity following conversations with the field. The [Recognition and Rewards roadmap](#) may provide an instrument to address these concerns. The Open Science NL programme will give a further boost on the ongoing Open Science developments and activities in the Netherlands

Sarah Coombs, Open Science advisor for the Universities of Applied Sciences

Next, Sarah Coombs welcomed the audience on behalf of the Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS). The DCC PO (Praktijkgericht Onderzoek”) developed their own ‘[Handreiking voor de Organisatie van Datastewardship voor praktijkgericht onderzoek van hogescholen](#)’, which was finalised in June 2022. The DCC-PO has the focus on supporting research supporters (in contrast to the other LDCCs, where the main focus is to support researchers). As the research function of Universities of Applied Sciences (UoAS) is relatively new, so are the jobs that are related to research support. Also, there is no unified job profile system yet for UoAS and it takes a lot more effort to get the data stewards job profile implemented. In addition, since, all the members of the Vereniging Hogescholen are very autonomous, there will be differences in the implementation and its time path.

Introducing the NPOS-F report

Mijke Jetten (Health-RI and co-author of the report) then introduced the 2021 “[Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education](#)” report, its recommendations, and the Data stewards job profile. At the origin of the report are the estimation that 3 fte datasteward are needed per 100 researchers and the challenges for building capacity building for data stewardship. The report contains a basic data steward job profile with tasks in three expertise areas: policy, infrastructure and research. The association of universities in the Netherlands (UvN) implemented the official data stewards job profile in their central job functioning system (UFO) so that universities can easily use the profile when recruiting and hiring data stewards. The report also contains data steward function profiles for the FUWAVAZ job classification system and for the UAS data steward profile. The report has been a great source of inspiration for many other countries wanting to professionalise data stewardship.

Figure 4.2 from the [report](#): Basic job profile components of a data steward

The report also contains recommendations, summarized:

Related to job profile components:

1. Formalise profiles
2. Adopt profiles
3. Create career perspectives
4. Allow diversity of roles and types
5. Adopt good practices
6. Secure positions

Related to training:

1. Standardise metadata for training
2. Align with (inter)national certification initiatives & providers

In the workshop we created a table from the summarized recommendations from the report and the 'Handreiking' and asked each speaker to assess the current state. Mijke's assessment of the current state of the recommendations on a national level:

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		For universities but not yet formalised for UMC and UAS	Dependency on formal job classification systems
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		Local and national communities (TDCC + Data Stewards Interest Group)	Strengthen collaboration and peer-to-peer learning
3.	Build data steward capacity		Disbalance: necessary and current FTE	Harmonise efforts + convincing stories
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		No certification + strengthen collaboration on a national level	Potential for initiatives such as RDNL, TDCCs and Open Science NL
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		Hiring and keeping DS is challenging	Support vs science embedment discussion

Use Cases on data stewards job profile implementation

Radboudumc

Professor of Bioinformatics (and FAIR data infrastructure) Peter-Bram 't Hoen presented the implementation of the data stewardship profile in Radboudumc. In 2019 he first approached HR with function descriptions, in 2021 the function descriptions were implemented in the local FUWAVAZ function grading system, and in 2022 the first employees were appointed as data steward. The discussions took place in parallel with the national NFU – FUWAVAZ coordination team (national implementation pending computer system updates) and NPOS Data steward task group. Data stewards can have three different profiles:

- a. (scale 9) Hands-on supporting research projects

- b. (scale 10) Additional responsibilities for implementation of data stewardship policies in research programs
- c. (scale 11) Additional responsibilities for defining data stewardship policies in a research institute

Currently, Radboudumc has 7 data stewards appointed in the formal data steward function descriptions . Many more data stewards are working at Radboudumc, appointed in other function descriptions and some more in a role rather than a function. The data steward network coordinated by the Radboud Technology Center Data Stewardship (Mirjam Brullemans) functions well and is connected to data stewards at Radboud University’s Research Data Management and data steward network. Training of data stewards is mostly informal (‘on the job’) and there is a focus on creating awareness and training of researchers. In Peter-Bram’s group, collaboration is promoted through “Friday data steward day”. Remaining challenges:

- **Lack of awareness** of the data steward profiles in certain departments and with some HR advisors
- **Difference with data manager** function profiles is often unclear
- **The career path a, b, c does not fit every data steward:** it is assuming that data stewards would like to gradually move from more hands-on project-related data stewardship to more policy-related activities.
- Data steward is **not recognised as a research function**. This means that we can only appoint data stewards for three years on a temporary contract instead of four and is a reason for using alternative profiles
- Data stewards **do not have a knowledge worker status**. This makes it difficult to recruit data stewards from outside EU when they are aged >30.

Current state of the recommendations for Radboudumc:

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		Implemented in local FUWAVAZ	Implemented in national FUWAVAZ
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		Local Data Steward Network and national Data Steward Interest group function well	In addition to internal network, create a face to the outside world (Professional society of data stewards)
3.	Build data steward capacity		Training from peer-peer; too little advanced courses available	Involved in development of expert trainings
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		Training mostly on-the-job	Organise advanced-level trainings and accreditation system
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		Not sure whether the career path a, b, c profiles fit every data steward	No concrete actions at the moment

Saxion University of Applied Sciences

Renate Mattiszik, data steward at Saxion Research Services and member of the DCC-PO working group for Data stewardship and training, then presented the work done by the DCC-PO. One of its objectives was to coordinate and professionalize data stewardship for Universities of Applied Sciences at a national level. From February 2021 to November 2022 13 UoAS worked on the [Handreiking voor de Organisatie van Datastewardship voor praktijkgericht onderzoek van hogescholen](#). The UoAS Job Profile consists of 8 expertise areas and 3 levels: junior/executive tasks, coordinating tasks and policy tasks.

Policy & Strategy	Compliance	Facilitating Good RDM Practices	RDM Service Management
RDM Infrastructure	Knowledge Management	Network and Communication	Data Sharing and Publishing

Remaining challenges:

- Every UoAS has its own job profile system
- Uniformity
- Funding
- Positioning within the organization
- Capacity building
- Necessity!

Current state of recommendations for Saxion University of Applied Sciences:

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No official formalization • HR approved of profile for job offer 	HR is looking into revising all job profiles concerning research
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SRS website and back office • RDM policy • no other tasks 	
3.	Build data steward capacity		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of sufficient funding • Discussion with management about higher job profiling 	Positioning library
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDNL • Training DCC-PO • DCC Spring Training days • Plenty on the job training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving training myself • DCC-PO Edubadges
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am the only one right now • I am already at the highest level 	Is playing a role as soon as other DSs are employed.

Technical University Delft

Yan Wang, the Data Stewardship coordinator at TU Delft presented the implementation of the data steward UFO profile. The TU Delft was the first university to adopt a data stewardship model with data stewards at the faculties and a central data stewardship coordinator at the library. Started as a pilot in 2017 it became a standard service in 2020. Both the data stewards and the coordinator were hired under the UFO profile specialist scientific information. Currently, the team is composed of 11 faculty data stewards, 1 library data steward and 1 coordinator. The process of implementing the official data stewards job profile started in November 2021 and involves the following steps and groups:

- The data stewards team started drafting an overview of common tasks and responsibilities of the data stewards,
- The library research data service brought and explained the overview to the library HR department for an assessment on the match with the UFO profile. The library HR department gave a general advice of the profile based on the common tasks and responsibilities provided.
- The advice was brought back to the faculties. The faculty secretaries and their HR departments did final review based on the complete tasks and responsibilities of their data stewards, and updated the profile eventually.

Since a positive advice was given in May 2022, faculties have started updating the profiles of their existing data stewards to the new profile, which often means a promotion. The data stewards UFO profile has been used in recruitment since 2022 and currently, 8 out of 12 Data Stewards have the corresponding UFO profile. Next is to update the rest Data Stewards' profile, and also to assess and update the Data Stewardship coordinator's profile. TU Delft evaluated the changes in the position and the candidates since 2017. As to the recruitment, the common tasks in job descriptions remain the same while more focus is paid on faculty-specific topics; the candidates still come from a research background (PhD / Postdoc). For the onboarding, training now mainly takes place online and on the job via team discussions and peer-support.

Remaining challenges:

- There is always a difference between the profile and a concrete position,, which makes it almost impossible to have a perfect match between them.
- Data Stewards' tasks vary across faculties in daily practices, library HR recommendation can only be generic on the 'common tasks' (baseline). Therefore a 2-step assessment is needed.
- There is a clear divide, in terms of HR policies, between academic and support roles in UFO system. The position of data steward is classified as a support role in UFO, but requires strong academic profiles which are more often found among international candidates.

Current state of the recommendations at TU Delft:

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		- UFO profile is used in new recruitment	- Complete the profile update for existing DS
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		- Well established DS team - Good visibility to researchers	- Improve communication channels and internal management
3.	Build data steward capacity		- Central and faculty level capacity in place (generic) - Lack of capacity on innovation - Lack of capacity at departmental / project level	- Develop and establish faculty level Data Stewardship
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		- A lot of materials and on job learning available. - But no certified formal education.	- Establish formal <u>on-boarding</u> for DS
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		- Salary scale up from UFO profile adoption - No clear career path for DS	- Follow EOOSC and RDA work on DS career path

Introduction to the international landscape

EOOSC & Data Stewardship, by Celia van Gelder, co-chair of the ‘[Data stewardship, curricula and career paths Task Force](#)’

The EOOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group published the report [Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science](#) in February 2021 with recommendations to enable the development of interoperable and qualified training for digital skills for FAIR and Open Science, for different stakeholders: policy makers & funders, Universities & research organisations, Competence centres, EOOSC Association, EOOSC projects.

The report describes 10 roles within the EOOSC ecosystem, one of which is the data steward / data librarian. The Dutch profile, together with the Danish profile, provided a use case in the skills chapter of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda ([SRIA](#), 2021, chapter 6.4) of the EOOSC: “Emerging approaches towards implementing FAIR data stewardship in Europe”. The Data stewardship, curricula and career paths Task Force focuses on the role of data stewards, their core activities, and curricula to ensure that they are internationally recognized and aligned. It has 25 members (+ 5 new members in 2022) who are experts from 18 European countries and main stakeholder groups: universities, national organisations/initiatives/infrastructures, EOOSC related projects, research infrastructures.

The Task Force advises the EOOSC-A Board and has two main work streams:

- *minimal curriculum for data stewards*
In April 2023 a milestone report is expected from the curriculum workstream: ‘Recommendations for Data Stewardship Skills, Training and Curricula’, containing national and institutional use cases. The Netherlands use case is in preparation.
- *career paths for data stewards*
The Career Paths Workstream focuses on the analysis of data stewardship career paths and is preparing a report and several workshops for 2023.

Celia stresses that the Task Force explicitly builds on existing work to prevent reinventing the wheel. Their approach is to:

- Actively engage with stakeholders and build on previous work: build, connect & consolidate
Examples: the RDA Group on Professionalizing Data Stewardship, EUA, other EOSC-A Task forces, and relevant projects (Skills4EOSC, EOSC-Future, etc)
- Identify (existing and new) use cases implementing data stewardship curricula and career paths
- Ensure a co-creation process between theoretical development and implementation examples
- Make current insights, experiences, implementation examples available (in a usable form) for all stakeholders

RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group, by Yan Wang, IG co-chair

The motivation to initialize the Interest group at RDA Plenary 14 were a lack of consensus on data stewards's responsibility, value, required knowledge and skills and no clear approach on building and keeping the DS capacity. In next plenaries a charter was written and 9 task groups (TG) formed to work on a business case, terminology, models for Data Stewardship, job profiles, training, career tracks, networking and certification. Mainly two areas of actions have been identified according to the work progress made so far:

1. Data Stewardship as a profession
TG 5: Research landscape of DS training + TG 6: Data Steward Career Tracks
Report: [Data Stewardship Landscape report](#) (2022)
Dataset: Landscape report [resource matrix](#) (2022)
2. Data Stewardship as a Service
Tg 1: Business case + Tg 3: Data Stewardship Models
Report: [Current Models of Data Stewardship Survey Report](#) (2022)
Dataset: [Models of Data Stewardship Survey Output Data](#) (2022)

Currently, TG 6 is working on the results of a survey on Data Stewards Career tracks for people who work on data steward-related activities. Preliminary results show that approx. 75 % do not have the job title 'data steward'.

Conclusions

Based on the presentations and the discussions in the break out groups (see below), the following take-away messages can be defined with regards to the recommendations discussed:

- Team up: make sure to involve all stakeholders in your organization to build capacity for data stewardship, including HR staff (who isn't always aware of the existence of the profile) and senior researchers or deans who can act as ambassadors for data stewardship
- Explore how overhead budget from research projects can be used to organize structural and sustainable data stewardship support

- Allow data stewards time to be part of the research team and recognize their efforts as part of the team's work
- Create clarity on the data stewardship tasks and make open science achievements such as open data or software competitive to make the case for investing in data stewardship for (faculty) boards
- Make FAIR and data stewardship meaningful by focusing less on compliance and more on societal responsibility
- Set up acknowledged professional training for data stewards and explore if a professional association is desirable (cf. software engineering societies or privacy officers associations)

Next steps per recommendation for all organisations

nr	Recommendation	All	Next steps
1	Formalization of job profile data steward		Create clarity on the data stewardship tasks and make open science achievements such as open data or software competitive to make the case for investing in data stewardship for (faculty) boards
2	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		
3	Build data steward capacity		<p>Team up: make sure to involve all stakeholders in your organization to build capacity for data stewardship, including HR staff (who isn't always aware of the existence of the profile) and senior researchers or deans who can act as ambassadors for data stewardship</p> <p>Explore how overhead budget from research projects can be used to organize structural and sustainable data stewardship support</p>

4	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		Set up acknowledged professional training for data stewards and explore if a professional association is desirable (cf. software engineering societies or privacy officers associations)
5	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		<p>Make FAIR and data stewardship meaningful by focusing less on compliance and more on societal responsibility</p> <p>Allow data stewards time to be part of the research team and recognize their efforts as part of the team's work</p>

Break out discussions

After the break, the group split up in three subgroups and were asked to come up with actionable steps related to the recommendations and these questions:

1. How to successfully implement the data stewards job profile and recruit data stewards?
2. How to organize national training and collaborate to increase capacity?

	Actions related to the job profile	Actions related to training & capacity building
Group 1	Get clarity about the role	<p>Have acknowledged certification for the data stewards (example privacy officers)</p> <p>Professional training</p> <p>Data engineers education</p> <p>Certification can be complex notion; domain should be taken into account</p>
Group 2	Maybe too much attention to the job title instead of	Organize national training

	<p>tasks list; research is evolving and new tasks arise, senior management not always aware. How to convince them; difference between faculties. What is mechanism to convince boards?</p> <p>Find ambassadors / e.g. deans</p> <p>Competition can help: show open data sets; software etc. (open science achievements)</p> <p>Compliance vs FAIR data: move from compliance to societal responsibility?</p>	
<p>Group 3</p>	<p>meaningful: create stories while collaborating (hanging out) with the communities</p> <p>awareness: team up with HR people for instance (by coordinators / research support head)</p> <p>sustainability: 'overhead' (15%) from research project funding should be used for structural data stewards mandatory! Requires system change</p>	